

CARBON REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES : PROBLEMS INVOLVED IN USING INDUSTRIAL ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to investigate and solve the problems inherent in the use of aluminium alloys containing a high level of alloying elements. Three examples are considered: (Al-4.5 Cu), (Al-10 Mg) and AS7G0.6 (A357). We will show that using these alloys implies the tailoring of the composite solidification in order to promote limited and localized microsegregation of primary phases and the optimization of the temperature and the duration of the solution treatment in order to avoid formation of Al_4C_3 at the fibre-matrix interface.

INTRODUCTION

For some years, numerous efforts have been devoted to the development and to the optimisation of fabrication processes of aluminium matrix composites reinforced with continuous carbon fibres [1-7]. At present composites can be realistically envisaged as structural elements or local reinforcements in aerospace and automotive components. In the case of local reinforcement the matrix alloys considered are industrial alloys which have to meet several specifications relative to the unreinforced part of the component in terms of yield strength, castability, etc..

The use of these industrial aluminium alloys as matrix in MMC can pose several problems related to the formation of unwanted phases such as reaction products between alloy elements and the carbon fibre during fabrication processing and subsequent heat treatments or large brittle intermetallic compounds forming during solidification. It has been shown that both types of phases can drastically affect the mechanical properties of metal matrix composites [8]. More specifically, the objective of this work is to study the problems caused by using highly alloyed matrices, such as Al-4.5Cu, Al-10Mg (wt. %) and AS7G0.6 (= A357) in carbon fibre reinforced metal matrix composites.

The main advantage of employing these alloys lies in their rather low liquidus temperature compared to those of pure aluminium or low-addition alloys. The gain is of the order of 25°C for Al-4.5Cu and Al-10Mg (wt. %) and of 50°C for AS7G0.6. Moreover it is important to note that a process based on the infiltration of a preform under moderate pressure and in isothermal conditions (the mould, the fibre preform and the liquid metal are all at the same temperature), such as the process developed at ONERA [9, 10] allows to take a definite advantage of this gain in temperature. With this process, if the pressure is sufficient (10 to 15 MPa), the infiltration is of excellent quality even for liquid metal temperatures 5°C higher than the alloy liquidus temperature. In these conditions, the reaction kinetics between carbon and aluminium can be sufficiently slowed down to avoid the deleterious effect of interfacial carbides. In this way, composites having high mechanical characteristics [11 and table 2] have been fabricated with uncoated high modulus carbon fibres with two typical durations of reaction between liquid metals and the carbon preform of the order of 60 and 600 s. This last result is particularly important as it allows to envisage the manufacture of bulk components requiring longer solidification durations.

However, the use of these alloys poses new problems :

- These alloys in the as-cast conditions, contain brittle phases, such as silicon particles or intermetallic compounds (Al_2Cu , Mg_5Al_8 , Mg_2Si) which may adversely affects the mechanical properties of a composite.

In the case of Al-4.5Cu and Al-10Mg alloys the primary phases present in the matrix can be dissolved in a solution treatment at 530°C and 415°C respectively. But during this treatment, carbides may form at the fibre/matrix interfaces, specially at the higher temperatures.

In the case of the AS7G0.6 alloy, the Mg_2Si phase can be dissolved at 540°C. However the poor solubility of silicon in solid aluminium renders impossible its dissolution. One way to avoid the detrimental effect of these brittle particles would be to interpose a coating between the fibres and the matrix. It has been shown, for example [11] that a pyrolytic carbon coating on the fibres can act as a mechanical fuse and thus restaure the mechanical properties of the composites.

- A last problem subsists concerning the optimization of the aging treatment. Due to the presence of numerous interfaces and to the small grain size, one might expect that the heterogeneous germination will be promoted at the expense of the homogeneous germination and that the precipitation kinetics will be accelerated. Therefore the optimised treatments for the matrix could be different than the treatments for the alloy in the unreinforced part, due to the difference in solidification conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Metal matrix composite plates ($80*38*1mm^3$) with unidirectional reinforcement have been fabricated at ONERA by liquid infiltration of carbon fibre preforms under moderate pressure (15 MPa). The details of the process are described in [9-10]. The volume fractions are determined by matrix dissolution. The heat treatments performed on the composites are either T4 (solution heat treated, cold water-quenched and naturally aged) or T6 (solution heat-treated, cold water-quenched and then artificially aged)

The constituents of the composites studied are listed in table 1. The systems have been selected for their rather low fibre/matrix reactivity in order to emphasize the effects associated with the heat treatments. The first two alloys have been elaborated starting from pure Al, Cu and Mg.

Two carbon fibres have been considered : a high modulus FT700 and a high strength (M40J). M40J fibres coated with a thin (100 nm) pyrolytic carbon layer applied by low pressure chemical vapour deposition [12] have also been considered.

Table 1. Constituents of the metal matrix composites

Matrix alloys	Composition (Wt. %)		
Al - 4.5 Cu	Al - 4.5Cu (elaboration : ONERA)		
Al - 10Mg	Al - 10Mg (elaboration : ONERA)		
AS7G0.6 (=A357)	Al - 6.7Si - 0.65Mg - 0.1Fe (supplier : Messier)		
Carbon fibres	Tensile strength(MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Supplier
FT 700 (3K filaments)	3300	700	Tonen
M40J (6K filaments)	4400	377	Toray
M40J/Cp	unchanged	unchanged	Onera

Longitudinal strengths have been determined from tensile tests performed on $80*8*1 mm^3$ test-pieces (mean value for 4 tests).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile strength data together with the fabrication and processing conditions of the various systems studied are presented in table 2. The structures are illustrated on the micrographs in figures 2 to 12.

PRELIMINARY REMARKS ON THE SOLIDIFICATION OF THE MATRIX IN COMPOSITES.

The solidification process of a metallic alloy is significantly affected by the presence of the fibre preform. This fact has been described and modelled by [13] in the case of a $Al_2O_3/Al-4.5Cu$ composite with a unidirectional solidification along the fibres.

In our case, the temperature gradient is perpendicular to the fibres and the cooling rate is of the order of $10^\circ C/min$ (the fibres are in contact with the liquid alloy during approximately 60 s).

The growth of the dendrite primary arms is constrained by the presence of the fibres to the interfibre volume (corresponding to distances of less than $10 \mu m$) and therefore the growth occurs predominantly in the direction perpendicular to the temperature gradient provoking the growth of the secondary arms and a coalescence of the dendrites. The liquid fraction remaining to solidify is rejected near towards the fibres. As a result, the microsegregation in this process is very limited and localised at the matrix/fibre interfaces. This explains the relatively small size of the primary phases compared with those found in unreinforced cast alloys and this is illustrated in figures 1a and 1b.

Table 2. Fabrication conditions and tensile strength of the composites studied. T_i and t_i represent the infiltration temperature and duration respectively.

Sample	Infiltration conditions		Heat treatments	Mean strength (MPa)	Volume fraction %	Figure
	T_i ($^\circ C$)	t_i (s)				
Al - 4.5Cu/ FT700	645	60	as - cast	1160 1350	53 58	2, 3
Al - 4.5Cu/ FT700	645	60	6h $530^\circ C$ + natural aging	930 1310	53 58	5
Al - 4.5Cu/ FT700	645	60	24h $530^\circ C$ + natural aging	830		6, 7
Al - 4.5Cu/ FT700	645	600	as - cast	1060 970	63 -	4
A357/M40J	620	60	as - cast	710	68	8
A357/M40J	620	60	16 h $540^\circ C$ +6h $160^\circ C$	220	75	10, 12

A357/M40J-Cp	620	60	as - cast	1360	72	9
A357/M40J-Cp	620	70	16h 540°C + 6h 160°C	344	72	11
Al-10Mg/ FT700	620	700	as - cast	1093 1346	63 55	
Al-10Mg/ M40J	620	70	as - cast	1304	65	

Composites with Al-4.5 Cu matrix

As can be seen in figure 3, the matrix of the as-cast composite contains small-sized primary Al_2Cu particles in the vicinity of the matrix/fibre interface. As they form at the end of the solidification process, one can reasonably think they are not adherent to the fibres. This explains why the tensile strength is fairly high (table 2). If the fibres are kept in contact with the liquid alloy during longer times (600 s instead of 60 s), the size of these phases is not affected. However, it is to be noticed that in this case Al_4C_3 phases form at the fibre/matrix interfaces in sufficiently large quantities to decrease the tensile strength (figure 4).

The solution treatment temperature being relatively high (530°C) such carbides could form during the heat treatments. However, given the small initial size of the Al_2Cu phases, the time has been limited to 6 hours. This results in a nearly complete dissolution of the Al_2Cu particles as can be seen in figure 5. Moreover, no carbides could be detected even by T.E.M. [14]. The tensile data after the T4 treatment show no decrease in the tensile strength. On the other hand, if the solution time is prolonged, Al_4C_3 form, as can be seen on figure 6, 7 with an associated drop in tensile strength (table 2).

As a conclusion in order to use this alloy it is necessary to infiltrate the preform and solidify the composite as quickly as possible and limit the duration of the solution treatment of the Al_2Cu phases. This can present some difficulty in the case of the fabrication of large components.

Composites with AS7G0.6 matrix

The same remarks as above apply concerning the solidification process. Inside the fibre preform the solidification conditions are such that the size of the Mg_2Si and Si particles are relatively small (below 1 μm , figure 8, 9) compared to the phases formed in the unreinforced alloy. It is to be noted though that the Si particles are numerous and that, locally, several fibres may be bridged by such a particle (with potentially deleterious effect). The presence of such particles could explain the relatively low tensile strength of the as-cast composite (about 700 MPa). A similar effect has been reported by [15] in squeeze-cast A357/Nicalon fibre system. Even for short solidification periods, typical in this process, silicon phases bridging several fibres are encountered, leading to a premature brittle fracture and a degradation in the mechanical properties of the composite. The solution, in our case, was found by interposing a thin carbon pyrolytic carbon coating on the fibres. This pyrolytic carbon interphase plays the role of a mechanical fuse which can deviate cracks [11]. Thus, as can be seen in table 2, the presence of such a coating permits to increase the tensile strength of as-cast composites from 710 MPa up to 1360 MPa. However, after the standard heat treatment for this alloy (solution treatment at 540°C for 16h followed by an aging treatment at 160°C for 6h) a significant drop in tensile strength is observed (cf. table 2) whether the fibres are coated or not. In both cases, metallographic examination of the composites plates show (figure 10, 11, 12), in addition to a spheroidisation of silicon particles, the presence of numerous Al_4C_3 particles resulting from a significant reaction between fibres and matrix. It is to be noted though that the presence of a thin Cp interphase must deviate cracks and this would explain why the drop is less in the M40J + Cp/AS7G0.6 system. TEM examination are under way to evaluate whether some carbon coating subsists on the fibres after the complete treatment.

This drop in properties after a heat treatment has also been observed by [15] on the A357/Nicalon fibre system heat treated during only 8 hours at 540°C (followed by an aging at 160°C for 6h).

As a conclusion it can be said that two difficulties arise with this matrix alloy related, one, to the presence of silicon particles and the other to the solution treatment duration.

The application of a thin carbon coating on the fibres proved to be beneficial. The choice of a less reactive fibre (for example high modulus FT700) whose superficial microstructure is similar to the Cp microstructure could limit the formation of aluminium carbides and trigger the mechanical fuse effect. In any case, the duration of the solution treatment will have to be decreased significantly, which must be possible given the small size of the Mg₂Si particles formed in this process. It has been shown [16] that for A357 alloy, the duration of heat treatment has little influence on the alloy mechanical characteristics so that an hour solution treatment is enough to reach the yield strength. On the other hand, increasing the duration of solution treatment promotes the spheroidisation of silicon particles and so increase the elongation and the fatigue behaviour of the alloy. So, we can think that an heat treatment optimization is possible for composites with A357 matrix.

Composites with Al-10Mg matrix

The results obtained on these composites are particularly good, even for long solidification times (table 2). This is attributed to the low solidification temperature of the composite, the liquidus temperature of the matrix alloy being 615°C. The temperature solution treatment for the Mg₅Al₈ phases being only 415°C, one is lead to think that it should not adversely affect the mechanical properties of the composite.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that it can be possible without damaging the composites to use industrial aluminium alloys. Their main advantage lies in their rather low liquidus temperature which allows the decrease of the fibre-matrix interaction. Using these alloys implies the tailoring of the composite solidification in order to promote limited and localized microsegregation of primary phases and the optimization of the temperature and the duration of the solution treatment in order to avoid formation of Al₄C₃ at the fibre-matrix interface. Nethertheless, it will be necessary, especially for the processing of bulk components, to use fibres with a rather high chemical inertia (high modulus fibres) or fibres coated with Cp coating in order to limit the fibre -matrix interaction and promote an interfacial debonding.

This work will be completed by a study of the effect of the aging treatment on the mechanical behaviour of the composites.

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FIGURES

Figure 1a. R357 Microstructure

Figure 1b. R357/M40J Microstructure

Figure2. Al_{4.5}Cu/FT700; as-cast

Figure3. as-cast; Al₂Cu phases

Figure4. Al_{4.5}Cu/FT700; as-cast
 $t_i = 600s$; Al₄C₃ formation

Figure5. Al_{4.5}Cu/FT700
solution treatment 6h 530°C

Figure6. Al_{4.5}Cu/FT700
solution treatment 24h 530°C

Figure7. 24h 530°C
Al₄C₃ formation

Figure 8. A357/M40J ; as-cast

Figure 9. A357/M40J-Cp; as-cast

Figure 10. A357/M40J ; 16h 540°C +6h 160°C; Si spheroidisation

Figure 11. A357/M40J-Cp; T6
Si spheroidisation
Al₄C₃ formation

Figure 12. A357/M40J; T6; Al₄C₃ formation